

PROJECT HATAW (HEALTH ADVOCACY THROUGH ACTIVE-DANCE WORKOUT) IN IMPROVING HEALTH-RELATED FITNESS AMONG GRADE 10 STUDENTS OF GEN. EMILIO AGUINALDO NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

Fitness is a universal concern of everyone. The purpose of this study was to assess PROJECT HATAW (Health Advocacy Through Active-dance Workout) in Improving Health- Related Fitness among Grade 10 Students of Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School. A revised physical fitness test developed by Department of Education pursuant to D.O. 34 series 2019 was utilized as part of the combination of quasi-experimental and descriptive research design. A total of 80 learners took part in the test. Paired Sample t-test was used to determine whether there was a difference in physical fitness test before and after 30 days of implementation of Project HATAW program. The study revealed that there was a statistically significant improvement on the following areas, BMI ($t(39)=0.58$, $p<0.568$, $d=0$), 3-minute Step Test: Before ($t(39)=7.93$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.25$), After ($t(39)=7.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.24$), Strength: Push Up ($t(39)=11.54$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.83$), Basic Plank ($t(39)=8.38$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.32$), Flexibility: Right ($t(39)=6.61$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.04$), Left ($t(39)=5.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.92$), and Sit and Reach ($t(39)=7.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.22$). It implies that Project HATAW is effective. Students should prioritize their health by performing daily dance exercise or any form of physical activities to achieve physically fit; teachers should be encouraged to do exercises like the Project HATAW to instill healthy mind and body; reduce from any health risks such hypertension, diabetes, obese and emotional stress; parents should be encouraged to be more of assistance in the fitness of their children; athletes should undergo and perform dance exercises to help improve their endurance, strength and flexibility; sports coaches should give time to dance exercises as a part of their training routines; and to stay healthy at all times; and a similar study is recommended utilizing Project HATAW to help improve and enhance students' fitness level.

Keywords: *fitness, dance-workout, healthy lifestyle, health-related fitness, physical fitness test*

INTRODUCTION

Physical fitness refers to the ability of the body systems to work together efficiently to allow one to be healthy and perform activities of daily living. Being efficient means doing daily activities with the least effort possible. A fit person is able to perform schoolwork, meet home responsibilities, and still have enough energy to enjoy sport and other leisure activities. A fit person can respond effectively to normal life situations, such as raking leaves at home, stocking shelves at a part-time job, and marching in the band at school. A fit person can also respond to emergency situations.

Physical health is a person's ability to convey physical activities that require strength, endurance and flexibility. The element that affects physical health is cardio-respiratory endurance. Cardiorespiratory endurance is the functional capacity of organs including heart, lungs and blood vessels to work optimally in a rest state and exercise in getting oxygen and then circulating oxygen to tissues used in the body's metabolic processes. Exercise is activities of body to do some movements including walking, jogging, running, jumping, swimming, dancing and so on in order to maintain and have better physical fitness. Physical activities must be planned properly, and done repetitively. Physical fitness is a set of attributes that are either health- or skill-related (Tolentino, 2012).

Physical activity in daily life can be categorized into occupational, sports, conditioning, household, or other activities. Exercise is a subset of physical activity that is planned, structured, and repetitive and has a final or an intermediate objective on the improvement or maintenance of physical fitness.

Physical fitness is a set of attributes that are either health- or skill-related. The degree to which people have these attributes can be measured with specific tests. These definitions are offered as an interpretational framework for comparing studies that relate physical activity, exercise, and physical fitness to health. In contrast with physical activity, which is related to the movements that people perform, physical fitness is a set of attributes that people have or achieved (Carbonell et al., 2012).

Physical exercise is vital for a healthy life and has several positive influences on the body. On the other hand, physical inactivity adversely influences body weight and is associated with obesity. In addition, exercise is an organized process where body and mind are continually defied with the pressure from various volumes (quantity) and intensity. There are two kinds of physical exercise, such as aerobic and anaerobic training. Aerobic exercise is an exercise that helps the heart and lungs work harder to supply muscles with oxygen, for example, aerobics, running, swimming and cycling. Aerobics is a brief exercise that does not require the use of oxygen to replenish fuel, for example: lifting weights and running short distances. Many sports can help maintain physical conditions, such as swimming, jogging, cycling, aerobic dance and zumba.

Zumba and high impact aerobics are physical activities that are currently preferred by teenagers and adult women. Aerobic high impact is one of the exercises consisting of strength training and routine stretching to improve all the elements of fitness the flexibility, muscle strength, and cardiovascular fitness. Aerobic high impact is usually done in classes that have been trained with the aim of increasing the intensity of exercise with the rhythm of music with a faster tempo. Zumba is a combination of a sports movement with a new dance featured a combination of music and dance. In addition, Zumba is acknowledged as a fun way to exercise and is beneficial in improving cardiovascular fitness. Furthermore, Zumba can help to reduce the skinfold thickness and body mass (Bompa & Gorgory, 2014).

Physical fitness is a state of health and well-being, more specifically, the ability to perform aspects of sports, occupations and daily activities. Physical fitness is generally achieved through proper nutrition, moderate-vigorous physical exercise, and sufficient rest. "Physical activity," "exercise," and "physical fitness" are terms that describe different concepts. However, they are often confused with one another, and the terms are sometimes used interchangeably. This paper proposes definitions to distinguish them. Physical activity is defined as any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that results in energy expenditure. The energy expenditure can be measured in kilocalories (Peter, 2016).

Being physically fit has been defined as "the ability to carry out daily tasks with vigor and alertness, without undue fatigue and with ample energy to enjoy leisure-time pursuits and to meet unforeseen emergencies." Although the definition may be conceptually sound, things such as vigor, alertness, fatigue, and enjoyment are not easily measured. On the other hand, a number of measurable components do contribute to physical fitness. The most frequently cited components fall into two groups: one related to health and the other related to skills that pertain more to athletic ability. The health-related components of physical fitness are (a) cardiorespiratory endurance, (b) muscular endurance, (c) muscular strength, (d) body composition, and (e) flexibility. Just as the amount of physical activity ranges from low to high, so does the level of physical fitness. Moreover, the levels of the five health-related components need not vary in concert; for example, a person may be strong but lack flexibility. The five health-related components of physical fitness are more important to public health than are the components related to athletic ability (Carbonell et al., 2012).

Background of the Study

The decline in adolescent's physical activity coincides with the current low levels of physical fitness in adolescents and the increasing rates of obesity (Cooper, 2016). Research shows that although all five aspects of physical fitness are important (body composition, cardiovascular fitness, flexibility, muscular strength, and muscular endurance), certain areas have greater associations with overweight and obesity than others. Cardiovascular fitness, for example, shows a stronger association with overweight and total adiposity, compared to other physical fitness components such as muscular fitness, speed/agility, or flexibility (Ara et al., 2017).

In regards to flexibility, studies have found contradicting results, some which show no association to weight status and others, which show a negative association between flexibility and obesity (Prista et al., 2013).

In studies that measure muscular strength and endurance, individuals that are overweight or obese typically perform poorer in both push-up and sit-up testing compared to their normal weight peers (Mak et al., 2016). However, these results must be interpreted cautiously, since lifting a greater body mass by overweight subjects involves higher energy costs (Deforche et al., 2013). The most common and adopted method for measuring weight status or obesity is through BMI (Phillips, 2012). With this knowledge of an association between BMI and cardiovascular fitness, it is important to look at other aspects that might affect this relationship. Health-related fitness knowledge is one such aspect that should be considered. Organizations such as American Association for Health, Physical Education, Recreation and Dance (AAHPERD) and National Association of Physical Education and Sport (NASPE), have addressed the importance of health-related fitness knowledge for many years and it is puzzling that more attention is not being given to health-related fitness knowledge as a possible method for changing current physical activity and obesity trends (Keating et al., 2013). While knowledge alone might not be enough to change physical activity behaviors, the lack of health-related fitness knowledge has been suggested to be a factor for the continued obesity epidemic in adolescents (Zapata et al., 2018). Therefore, increasing health-related fitness knowledge may lead to the increase in physical activity behaviors (Keating et al., 2013). However, despite the importance of educating adolescents on health-related fitness knowledge, the few studies previously done show conflicting results (Fitzgerald et al., 2012).

Most of the Grade 10 learners are not physically fit, inactive, and obese based on their BMI that were gathered during their Physical Fitness Test. These are some of the reasons why the researcher needs to take action and address the needs of the students in order for them to learn, perform and respond better. Thus, this Project HATAW would be an eye opener for them with dancing or aerobics and other form of exercises can help develop and improve their aspects in life.

As a Physical Educator who is molding the students holistically, it would be better to have learners who are physically, emotionally, mentally, and spiritually healthy all the time. However, the Grade 10 Students of Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School, Ramon, Isabela, are not good in terms of their physical condition because they neglected to have daily exercises because of mobile games, laziness, and other factors which cause inactive in doing physical activities, most especially in this time of pandemic and with the existing way of learning. This opens my mind to give action to what they are experiencing by uplifting, improving and developing their physical conditions for them to perform better, and they may be away from the contagious disease or virus, the COVID19.

The purpose of this study is to assess the Project HATAW (Health Advocacy Through Active-dance Workout) in improving health-related fitness among Grade 10 students of Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School.

Research Questions

1. What is the average health-related fitness level of the students before the implementation of the Project HATAW in terms of:
 - 1.1. Body Composition
 - 1.2. Cardiovascular Endurance
 - 1.3. Strength
 - 1.4. Flexibility
2. What is the average health-related fitness level of the students after the implementation of the Project HATAW in terms of:
 - 2.1. Body Composition
 - 2.2. Cardiovascular Endurance
 - 2.3. Strength
 - 2.4. Flexibility
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students after the implementation of Project HATAW ?
4. What is the effect size of the Project HATAW in improving the health-related fitness level of the students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This action research study utilized experimental design particularly the Quasi-Experimental design. Quasi-experiments are studies that aim to evaluate interventions but that do not use randomization. Similar to randomized trials, quasi-experiments aim to demonstrate causality between an intervention and an outcome. Quasi-experimental studies can use both pre-intervention and post intervention measurements, as well as non-randomly selected control groups. Thus, quasi-experimental research, is research that resembles experimental research, but is not true experimental research. Although the independent variable is manipulated, participants are not randomly assigned to conditions or orders of conditions (Cook & Campbell, 2019).

Because the independent variable is manipulated before the dependent variable is measured, quasi-experimental research eliminates the directionality problem. But because participants are not randomly assigned—making it likely that there are other differences between conditions—quasi-experimental research does not eliminate the problem of confounding variables. In terms of internal validity, therefore, quasi-experiments are generally somewhere between correlational studies and true experiments.

The quasi-experimental, sometimes called the pre-post intervention design, is often used to evaluate the benefits of specific interventions. Thus, this study will specifically use quasi-experimental to assess Project HATAW (Health Advocacy Through

Active-dance Workout) in improving the health-related fitness among Grade 10 students of Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School.

Study Site and Participants

This study was conducted in public school in the Legislative District 3- Ramon District particularly Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School, Gen. Aguinaldo, Ramon, Isabela. Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School caters Junior and Senior High School. The participants of the study are the learners.

Population, Sample Size, Sampling Method

The respondents of this study are the selected Grade 10 students enrolled in the school year 2021-2022 at Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School. The total population of the grade 10 students is 149.

A sample size of 80 students were determined and were selected using random sampling. The participants were divided into two groups with 40 participants for the control group and 40 participants for the experimental group. The control group utilized the intervention dance-workout, while the experimental group without the use of intervention.

Instruments

The primary assessment tool used in the study is questionnaire adopted from the DepEd Order No-34, s. 2019. It is composed of two parts, namely: Part 1 (Demographic Profile of the Respondents; Part 2 (Health-Related Fitness Test). It has four components with four items composed of A. Body Composition with 1 subsection (Body Mass Index), B. Cardiovascular Endurance with one subsection (3-Minute Step Test), C. Strength with two subsections (Push-up and Basic Plank), D. Flexibility with two subsections (Zipper Test and Sit and Reach). Components and performances can be interpreted and leveled to their respective scores and points namely Excellent, Very Good, Fair, Needs Improvements, and Poor.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through channels to conduct the study. The researcher also communicated with the school head about the objective of the study and solicited their approval in the distribution and administering of the Physical Fitness Test to the respondents.

The Physical Fitness Test Individual Score Card were distributed personally to the participants to ensure a hundred percent of the actual performance of the different tests.

Pre-Physical Fitness Test were done by both groups in the scheduled time and day. Control Group performed 30 minutes dance-workout every morning from 7:00 to 7:30 in the morning Monday to Sunday for a period of one month starting the day after the pre-

test, while experimental group performed their daily routine with the same period or duration.

Post-Physical Fitness Test were done simultaneously with the presence of the researcher to ensure a hundred percent actual performance and retrieval of the Individual Score Card.

Data Analysis

The responses gathered from the two groups through the questionnaire were tallied, tabulated, and computed to facilitate the analysis and interpretation of data using Microsoft Excel.

The following statistical tools were used:

1. The mean and standard deviation was used to determine data set.
2. The T-Test was used to determine the means of two groups.
3. The Eta-Square was used to determine the effect size.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher protected the participants' right to self-determination, anonymity and confidentiality. For this reason, the participants were given full information on the nature of the study through written informed consent which were distributed with the questionnaire. The data will be kept confidentially by not giving information to others and the participants were assured of their right to withdraw at any time. The names of the participants were not recorded and all with the data that were rendered.

RESULTS

Part 1. Average Health-Related Fitness Level of the Students Before the Implementation of Project HATAW.

Table 1 shows the average health-related fitness level of the students before the implementation of Project HATAW.

Table 1 Average Health-Related Fitness Level of Students Before The Implementation of Project HATAW

HEALTH-RELATED FITNESS TEST	ACTIVITY		CONTROL GROUP		EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	
			AVE.	REMARKS	AVE.	REMARKS
BODY COMPOSITION		BMI	20.23	Normal	21.20	Normal

CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE	3-Minute Step Test	Training Heart Rate	119.43	Good	120.10	Good
		Recovery Heart Rate	74.45	Good	83	Good
STRENGTH		Push Up	9.65	Fair	12	Good
		Basic Plank	3.90	Good	4	Very Good
FLEXIBILITY	Zipper Test	Right	3.43	Good	3.90	Good
		Left	3.35	Good	3.50	Good
	Sit and Reach	Final Score	48.50	Very Good	50.10	Very Good

As revealed in Table 1, the average health-related fitness level of the students the implementation of the Project HATAW are the following: Body Composition on BMI Average were 20.23 for control group and 21.20 for experimental group which resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on a 3 –minute step test training heart rate was 119.43 for control group, and 120.10 for experimental group which resulted to Good; recovery heart rate was 74.45 for control group and 83 for experimental group which resulted to Good; Strength on Push Up Test with 9.65 for control group which resulted to Fair and 12 for experimental group which is Good and Basic Plank with 3.90 for control group which resulted to Good and 4 for experimental group which resulted to Very Good; Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 3.43 for control group and 3.90 for experimental group and Left about 3.35 for control group and 3.50 for experimental group which both resulted to Good and to Sit and reach with the final score of 48.50 for control group and 50.70 for experimental group which resulted to Very Good.

Part 2. Average Health-Related Fitness Level of the Students After the Implementation of Project HATAW.

Table 2 shows the average health-related fitness level of the students after the implementation of Project HATAW.

Table 2 Average Health-Related Fitness Level of the Students After the Implementation of Project HATAW

HEALTH-RELATED FITNESS TEST	ACTIVITY		CONTROL GROUP		EXPERIMENTAL GROUP	
			AVE.	REMARKS	AVE.	REMARKS
BODY COMPOSITION		BMI	20.45	Normal	19.5	Normal
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE	3-Minute Step	Training Heart Rate	129.30	Excellent	130	Excellent

	Test	Recovery Heart Rate	82.95	Excellent	85.20	Excellent
STRENGTH		Push Up	11.08	Good	17.10	Very Good
		Basic Plank	6.03	Excellent	6.15	Excellent
FLEXIBILITY	Zipper Test	Right	4.08	Very Good	5	Excellent
		Left	4.00	Very Good	5	Excellent
	Sit and Reach	Final Score	56.10	Very Good	61.20	Excellent

As revealed in Table 2, the average health-related fitness level of the students after the implementation of the Project HATAW are the following: Body Composition the BMI Average were 20.45 for control group and 19.5 for experimental group which resulted to Normal; Cardiovascular Endurance on a 3 –minute step test training heart rate was 129.30 for control group and 130 for experimental group which resulted to Excellent; recovery heart rate was 82.95 for control group and 85.20 for experimental group which resulted to Excellent; Strength on Push Up Test with 11.08 for control group which resulted to good and 17.10 for experimental group which resulted to Very Good; Basic Plank with 6.03 for control group and 6.15 for experimental group which resulted to Excellent; and Flexibility on Zipper Test Right reached about 4.08 for control group which resulted to Very Good and 5 for experimental group which resulted to Excellent and Left about 4.00 for control group which resulted to Very Good and 5 for experimental group which resulted to Excellent and for Sit and reach with the final score of 56.10 for control group which resulted to Very Good and 61.20 for experimental group which resulted to Excellent.

Part 3. Significant Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores After the Implementation of the Project HATAW.

Table 3 shows the significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the students after the implementation of Project HATAW.

Table 3 Significant Difference Between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Students After the Implementation of Project HATAW

HEALTH-RELATED FITNESS TEST		N	M	SD	T	Df	p-value	
BODY COMPOSITION								
BMI	Pre-Test	40	20.63	3.74	0.58	39	.568	
	Post-Test	40	20.45	2.24				
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE								
3-MIN STEP TEST	Training Heart Rate	Pre-Test	40	119.43	7.93	39	.001	
		Post-Test	40	129.30				26.90
	Training Heart Rate	Pre-Test	40	74.45	7.83	39	.001	
		Post-Test	40	82.95				19.87
STRENGTH								
PUSH UP		Pre-Test	40	9.65	6.51	11.54	39	.001

		Post-Test	40	11.08	6.42			
BASIC PLANK		Pre-Test	40	3.90	3.20	8.38	39	.001
		Post-Test	40	6.03	3.13			
FLEXIBILITY								
ZIPPER TEST	RIGHT	Pre-Test	40	3.43	1.24	6.61	39	.001
		Post-Test	40	4.08	0.89			
	LEFT	Pre-Test	40	3.35	1.03	5.83	39	.001
		Post-Test	40	3.90	0.67			
Sit and Reach	FINAL	Pre-Test	40	48.50	24.90	7.75	39	.001
		Post-Test	40	56.10	22.50			

As shown in Table 3, Paired Sample T-test was conducted to determine whether there was a difference between the pretest and posttest scores the implementation of Project HATAW. The test result revealed that there is a statistically significant difference on the following areas, BMI ($t(39)=0.58$, $p<0.568$, $d=0$), 3-minute Step Test: Training Heart Rate ($t(39)=7.93$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.25$), Recovery Heart Rate ($t(39)=7.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.24$), Strength: Push Up ($t(39)=11.54$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.83$), Basic Plank ($t(39)=8.38$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.32$), Flexibility: Right ($t(39)=6.61$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.04$), Left ($t(39)=5.83$, $p<0.001$, $d=0.92$), and Sit and Reach ($t(39)=7.75$, $p<0.001$, $d=1.22$).

Part 4. Effect Size of the Project HATAW in Improving the Health-Related Fitness Level of the Students.

Table 4 shows the effect size of the Project HATAW in improving the fitness level of the students.

Table 4. Effect Size of the Project HATAW in Improving the Health-Related Fitness Level of the Students

HEALTH-RELATED FITNESS TEST		EFFECT SIZE
BODY COMPOSITION		
	BMI	0.012
CARDIOVASCULAR ENDURANCE		
3-MINUTE STEP TEST	Training Heart Rate	1.25
	Recovery Heart Rate	1.24
STRENGTH		
	Push Up	1.83
	Basic Plank	1.32
FLEXIBILITY		
Zipper Test	Right	1.04
	Left	0.92
Sit and Reach	Final	1.22

As revealed in Table 4, the effect size of the Project HATAW in improving the fitness level of the students were as follows: body composition is 0.012, 3-minute step test training heart rate is 1.25 and recovery heart rate is 1.24, push up is 1.83, basic plank

is 1.32, zipper test right 1.04 and left is 0.92, and sit and reach final is 1.22. The results revealed that there is a huge effect of Project HATAW in improving the health-related fitness level of the students. Therefore, Project HATAW had improved the health-related fitness level of the students.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study is to assess the Project HATAW (Health Advocacy Through Active-dance Workout) in improving health-related fitness among Grade 10 students of Gen. Emilio Aguinaldo National High School.

The average health-related fitness level of both groups of students before the implementation of Project HATAW was the following: for Body Composition, the BMI is Normal. For Cardiovascular Endurance, the 3-Minute Step Test (training heart rate as well as recovery heart rate) is Good. For Strength, Push-up is Good, and the Basic Plank is Very Good. For Flexibility, the Zipper Test (right and left) is Good, and Sit and Reach the final is Very Good.

The average health-related fitness level of both groups of students after the implementation of Project HATAW is the following: for Body Composition, the BMI is Normal; for Cardiovascular Endurance, the 3-Minute Step Test (training heart rate as well as recovery heart rate) is Excellent. For Strength, the Push-up is Very Good, and the Basic Plank is Excellent. For Flexibility, the Zipper Test (right and left) is Excellent, and the Sit and Reach final is Excellent.

The paired sample T-test revealed that there is a statistically significant difference in the pretest and post test scores of the students after the implementation of Project HATAW in terms of following areas: BMI, 3-Minute Step Test (training heart rate as well as recovery heart rate), Push-up, Basic Plank, Zipper Test (right and left), and Sit and Reach.

The result of the effect size revealed that there is a huge effect of Project HATAW in improving the health-related fitness level of the students. Therefore, Project HATAW improved the health-related fitness of the students.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The average health-related fitness level of the students before the implementation of Project HATAW was generally Good in terms of Body Composition, Cardiovascular Endurance, Strength, and Flexibility.
2. The average health-related fitness level of the students after the implementation of Project HATAW was generally Excellent in terms of Body Composition, Cardiovascular Endurance, Strength, and Flexibility.
3. There is a significant difference in the pretest and post-test scores of the students after the implementation of Project HATAW.

4. There is a huge effect of the Project HATAW in improving the health-related fitness level of the students.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are hereby recommended:

1. Students should balance their studies with their health conditions by performing the physical fitness activities they learned from Project HATAW on a regular basis.
2. Teachers are encouraged to instill in their students the value of a healthy mind and body in order to lower the risk of conditions like emotional stress, obesity, hypertension, and diabetes.
3. School principals may consider implementing Project HATAW as an intervention in their respective schools to improve physical fitness and health awareness.
4. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies to develop other intervention strategies to improve their organization's health and wellness.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

To meet the ethical consideration of the study, the researcher complied with the ethical and legal requirements related to the conduct of the study. The parents of the participants were notified and signed the informed consent form that include their decision in case they decided to withdraw or discontinue their participation from the study anytime, not expose them to any pressure or harm, kept their anonymity where no one will have access to the information about them and much more be disclosed with others.

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